

Conductometric Study of the Reaction between Zinc Salts and Alkali

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In the conductometric titrations of zinc sulphate with NaOH and the reverse, inflections are often sharp, but do not lead to a simple quantitative significance. Pure $Zn(OH)_2$ is formed only when the concentration of NaOH in the cell is about $N/100$ or less and $ZnSO_4$ is added. The same result is obtained when one starts with a mixture of $ZnSO_4$ and NaOH (excess) in the cell and titrates with HCl. The anomalies may be ascribed to the adsorption of $ZnSO_4$, on the one hand, and Na_2ZnO_2 , on the other, by $Zn(OH)_2$. These anomalies disappear when $Zn(NO_3)_2$ is used in place of $ZnSO_4$.

In an earlier paper¹ we have investigated the reaction between aluminium nitrate and alkali. We found that in all cases, where Al^{3+} and NO_3^- ions were in excess during titration, the results were far from those required for the formation of $Al(OH)_3$. The best procedure was addition of $Al(NO_3)_3$ to a dilute solution of NaOH (at least about $N/100$). We felt that a careful examination of the reactions between zinc sulphate/zinc nitrate and sodium hydroxide was also called for and started this work. Several earlier workers carried out similar investigations, but the results appeared somewhat confusing, e.g., Haldar², Carriere³, Berton⁴, Mendes⁵, Denk and Dewald⁶, Britton⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stock solutions of A. R. grade zinc sulphate, zinc nitrate, sodium hydroxide, and hydrochloric acid were prepared and accurately standardised by gravimetric and volumetric methods. These solutions were diluted according to requirements with conductivity water. The strengths of the stocks, maintained in reliable glass-stoppered containers, were checked at suitable intervals. The conductometric titration set was the same as

1. This *Journal*, 1960, 37, 785.
2. *Ibid.*, 1946, 23, 183.
3. *Chim. anal.*, 1947, 29, 83.
4. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 280.
5. *Compt. rend.*, 1948, 226, 916.
6. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1952, 268, 169.
7. "Hydrogen Ions", Vol II, p. 76, Chapman and Hall, 1956.

described in the earlier paper¹. The results are recorded in Tables I and II and shown graphically in Figs. 1, 2, 3 (for zinc sulphate) and 4 (for zinc nitrate). The number of graphs corresponds to the serial numbers in Table I and II.

TABLE I

No.	Cell.	Burette.	Inflec found.	Remarks
1.	0.545N-ZnSO ₄ , 4ml + water, 16 ml	1.01N-NaOH	1.70ml	31°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 2.16 ml. Reqd. for 4 Zn(OH) ₂ -ZnSO ₄ : 1.73ml.
2.	0.535N- ZnSO ₄ , 4 ml+ water, 36ml	..	1.73	28.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 2.12 ml. Reqd. for 4Zn(OH) ₂ - ZnSO ₄ : 1.683ml.
3.	0.5347N-ZnSO ₄ , 2 ml+ water, 78 ml	1.02N-NaOH	0.85	25.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.048 ml. Reqd. for 4Zn(OH) ₂ - ZnSO ₄ : 0.714ml.
4.	0.5347N-ZnSO ₄ , 2ml+ water, 148 ml	..	0.875	25°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.048 ml. Reqd. for 5 Zn(OH) ₂ - ZnSO ₄ : 0.87 ml.
5.	1.01N-NaOH, 1ml+ water, 19ml	0.535N-ZnSO ₄	(i) 0.93 (ii) 1.73	27°. Hardly any break at Na ₂ ZnO ₂ (arrow). Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.89 ml. Salt formed for 2nd break: 2l Zn(OH) ₂ - 2 Na ₂ ZnO ₂ .
6.	1.01N-NaOH, 1ml+ water, 39 ml	..	1.73	28.5°. Adsorption compound or mixture of 2lZn(OH) ₂ - 2 Na ₂ ZnO ₂ .
7.	1.01N-NaOH, 1ml+ 0.5N-Na ₂ SO ₄ , 2ml+ water, 37ml	..	1.76	28.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.89ml. Break = 27Zn(OH) ₂ . 2Na ₂ ZnO ₂ .
8.	1.01N-NaOH, 1ml + water, 79ml	535N-ZnSO ₄	(i) 1.83 (ii) 2.40 (iii) 1.9 (extrapolated)	24.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.88 ml. 1st break = 29Zn(OH) ₂ -Na ₂ ZnO ₂ . Reqd for 4Zn(OH) ₂ - ZnSO ₄ : 2.35ml.
9.	1.02N-NaOH, 1ml+ water, 149ml	0.5347N-ZnSO ₄	(i) 1.8 (ii) 2.6 (iii) 1.9 (extrapolated)	25.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.9 ml. Reqd. for 3Zn(OH) ₂ - ZnSO ₄ : 2.53ml
10.	0.535N-ZnSO ₄ , 10ml+ 1.01N-NaOH, 7ml+ water, 23ml	1.008N-HCl	For NaOH left : 1.725ml	25°. Reqd. for NaOH left: 1.74 ml; titration not continued to ZnCl ₂ stage.
11.	0.545N-ZnSO ₄ , 10ml+ 1.01N-NaOH, 10ml+ water 30ml	..	For NaOH left : 4.60ml	28.0°. Reqd. for NaOH left: 4.61 ml.
12.	0.5347N-ZnSO ₄ , 1ml+ 1.02N-NaOH, 3ml+ water, 36ml	1.02N-HCl	For NaOH left: 2.35ml; for ZnCl ₂ stage : 3.00ml	25.0°. Reqd. for NaOH left, 2.476ml. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ stage: 0.524ml. NaOH found: 0.650ml. NaOH. reqd. for ZnCl ₂ stage: 3.00ml of HCl.

TABLE II

No.	Cell.	Burette.	Inflec. found	Remarks.
1.	0.4674N-Zn(NO ₃) ₂ , 4ml + water, 36ml	1.02N-NaOH	1.830ml	25.0°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 1.83ml.
2.	1.01N-NaOH, 1ml+ water, 79ml	0.4674N-Zn(NO ₃) ₂	2.125	25°. Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 2.16ml.
3.	1.02N-NaOH, 1ml+ water, 103ml	„	2.150	25°, Reqd. for Zn(OH) ₂ : 2.18ml.
4.	0.4674N-Zn(NO ₃) ₂ , 10ml+ 1.01N-NaOH, 7ml + water, 23ml	1.008N-HCl	2.300	22.5°. Reqd. for NaOH left: 2.376 ml. (Titration not continued to ZnCl ₂ stage)
5.	0.4674N-Zn(NO ₃) ₂ , 1ml+ 1.01N-NaOH, 3ml+ water, 36ml	„	(i) 2.500 (ii) 3.000	25.0°. Reqd. for NaOH left: 2.54 ml. Reqd. for ZnCl ₂ stage: 3.00 ml

DISCUSSION

We have seen in the previous work¹ that when one starts with Al(NO₃)₃ in the cell and adds NaOH from the burette, the inflections, in general, show that some of the salt remains unchanged. The nature of discrepancy shows that in such cases some salt is retained by Al(OH)₃ due to adsorption. Since the nitrate ion can be adsorbed only feebly, the primary layer must be mostly of Al³⁺ ions. In the case of ZnSO₄, both the ions are likely to be adsorbed fairly strongly by virtue of their bivalency. Since the substrate is basic, the primary layer is more likely to be of the sulphate ions. Adsorption should be more pronounced in stronger solutions of the salt.

On the other hand, when one starts with NaOH in the cell and local concentration of the salt is minimised by vigorous stirring at every stage of addition, neither the Na⁺ nor the OH⁻ (which is in excess so long the equivalence point is not reached) will be strongly adsorbed and the equivalence point is more likely to correspond correctly to the inflection as was demonstrated, for example, by Kolthoff².

It is therefore to be expected that when we start with ZnSO₄ or Zn(NO₃)₂ in the cell, the results should be better, the more dilute the original solution, since the loss due to adsorption will then be less. In the reversed titrations, the results should be more satisfactory. Table I shows that these expectations are fulfilled. There is a steady improvement in favour of Zn(OH)₂ in the titrations No. 1 to 4 as the initial dilution of ZnSO₄ is increased. The results are much improved in the reverse titrations No. 5 to 9. Indeed, in the last two, the extrapolated values are almost quantitatively correct.

When one uses Zn(NO₃)₂, the results are surprisingly good (Table II). The results are quantitative whether one starts with the salt solution in the cell or alkali. This behaviour strongly indicates that with zinc salts the primary adsorbed layer on Zn(OH)₂

8. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1920, **112**, 172.

must be the anion (sulphate or nitrate). Since the nitrate, due to its uni-valency, can be only feebly adsorbed, there is little loss of Zn^{2+} by binding in the secondary layer.

FIG. 1. $ZnSO_4$ with $NaOH$.

FIG. 2. $NaOH$ with $ZnSO_4$.

It will be seen from the last column of Table I, that it is tempting to assume the existence of compounds like $4Zn(OH)_2 \cdot ZnSO_4^9$. Although there is indication of a little rounding at the breaks in some cases, they are still too sharp to be wholly ascribed to adsorption. A comparison of these results with those observed earlier for aluminium nitrate¹⁰ shows that there is little tendency towards the formation of salts like $Na_2ZnO_4^{10}$.

In order to convert all the $Zn(OH)_2$ formed into Na_2ZnO_4 , we require four moles of $NaOH$ for every mole of salt. All the zinc should then be in solution so that if a back titration of the excess $NaOH$ is tried, the end point should not be affected by adsorption of Zn^{2+} ions. Titration No. 11 in Table I, and No. 5 in Table II fulfil this expectation. When the proportion of $NaOH$ added is less, considerable discrepancies appear (Table II, No. 4). If the titration is continued, the $ZnCl_2$ stage is accurately located. It may be noted that in preparing the initial mixture of zinc salt and $NaOH$, different results are to be expected from different modes of mixing. Adding the zinc salt to $NaOH$ with vigorous stirring is

9. Heubel, *Compt. rend.*, 1945, 220, 280.

10. Heubel, *Ann. Chem.*, 1949, 4, 690.

likely to give better results than the reverse procedure. Thus, in Table I, No. 10, though the proportion of Zn : NaOH is less than 1:3, the $Zn(OH)_2$ stage is accurately located.

HCl (ml).
FIG. 3. $ZnSO_4 + NaOH$ with HCl.

$Zn(NO_3)_2 + NaOH$ and reverse. $Zn(NO_3)_2 + NaOH$ with HCl.

Titrant (ml).
FIG. 4

Addition of a small quantity of Na_2SO_4 to NaOH before titrating with $ZnSO_4$ (Table I, No. 7) appears to improve the results.

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